

Platyla merillaensis (Gastropoda, Aciculidae) a new species from Cantabria (N of Spain)

Platyla merillaensis (Gastropoda, Aciculidae) nueva especie de Cantabria (N de España)

Sergio QUIÑONERO-SALGADO*, Jesús RUIZ COBO** & Emilio ROLÁN***

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Platyla* is described, which was found in a cave in Cantabria (N Spain). It has important differences compared to other species of the genus described in Spain, particularly regarding measurements.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del género *Platyla* encontrada en una cueva de Cantabria (N España). Presenta diferencias notables comparadas con las especies del género descritas en España, particularmente en sus valores métricos.

INTRODUCTION

The family Aciculidae J.E. Gray, 1850 includes terrestrial prosobranch gastropoda, which have small size, turriculated shells with a variable sculpture. These species inhabit shady habitats or caves, always with high humidity levels. The family includes four genera: *Acicula* Hartmann, 1821; *Menkia* Boeters, Gittenberger & Subai, 1986; *Platyla* Moquin-Tandon, 1856; and *Renea* Nevill, 1880.

Of these four genera, three are present in Spain: *Acicula*, *Menkia* and *Platyla* (BOETERS, GITTENBERGER & SUBAI, 1989; BECH, 1990; GITTENBERGER, 1991; ALTONAGA ET AL., 1994; ROLÁN, 2003; MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ & ROBLES, 2005;

CADEVALL & OROZCO 2016). The genus *Platyla* is represented in Spain (including Balearic islands) by six species: *Platyla callostoma* (Clessin, 1911) has been cited in Catalonia, Asturias and Cantabria; *Platyla cryptomena* (De Folin & Bérillon, 1877) and *Platyla dupuyi* (Paladilhe, 1868) in the north of Spain; *Platyla hedionda* Torres Alba, 2012 in Andalusia; *Platyla polita* (W. Hartmann, 1840) in the Valencian Community; and *Platyla jordai* Altaba, 2013 in Mallorca (Balearic islands) (BOETERS ET AL., 1989; BECH, 1990; ALTONAGA ET AL., 1994; MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ & ROBLES, 2005; ALTABA, 2013; CADEVALL & OROZCO, 2016).

* Associació Catalana de Malacologia, Museu Blau, Plaça Leonardo da Vinci 4-5, 08019 Barcelona, Spain. sergioqs85@hotmail.com

** Grupo de Espeleología e Investigaciones Subterráneas Carballo/Raba, c/ Alcalde Arche s/n 39600- Muriedas, Cantabria, Spain.

*** Museo de Historia Natural de la Universidad de Santiago, Campus Norte, Parque Vista Alegre, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

Figure 1. Map of Cantabria showing the area of the Covallarco cave with a circle.

Figura 1. Mapa de Cantabria señalando la zona de la cueva de Covallarco con un círculo.

In the present work, a new species of the genus *Platyla* is described from Cantabria.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The studied specimens were found in sediments collected inside the cave of Covallarco, Merilla, municipality of San Roque de Riomiera, Cantabria, Spain (Figure 1). The collected samples were dried, separated on a set of sieves of 5 mm, 2mm, 1mm and 0,5 mm, then sorted and observed under a stereomicroscope.

Abbreviations

CACTI Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación, Universidad de Vigo

CACTUS Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

MZB Museu de Ciències Naturals de Barcelona, Spain.

UPV/EHU-FC Colección de Fauna Cavernícola (Departamento de Zoología) de la Universidad del País Vasco-Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, Bilbao, Spain.

CSQ Collection Sergio Quiñonero

SYSTEMATICS

Family ACICULIDAE J.E. Gray, 1850

Genus *Platyla* Moquin-Tandon, 1856

Type species: *Acme dupuyi* Paladilhe, 1868 (type by subsequent designation under ICZN art. 70.3.2, Welter-Schultes, 2012)

Platyla merillaensis n. sp. (Figures 2 & 3)

Type material: Holotype (Figure 2) MZB 2017-0448, shell. Paratypes: UPV/EHU-FC 4725, 2 shells; CSQ: 1 shell (Figure 3).

Type locality: Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla, San Roque de Riomiera (Cantabria), UTM: 30TVN48, altitude 395 m (Figures 1 and 4).

This cavity opens in the north skirt of Castro, in the northwest side of a large doline situated in the lower part of the hillside. The valley of the Carvajal stream, situated within the doline, is a typical formation in this part of the calcareous Cantabrian Mountains, with steep slopes and a narrow

Figure 2. *Platyla merillaensis* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 2.24 mm in height (Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla); C: protoconch; D, E: microsculpture and detail of the beginning of the protoconch; F, G: microsculpture and detail of the end of the protoconch.

Figura 2. Platyla merillaensis n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 2.24 mm de altura (Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla); C: protoconcha; D, E: microescultura y detalle del inicio de la protoconcha; F, G: microescultura y detalle del final de la protoconcha.

Figure 3. *Platyla merillaensis* n. sp. Paratype (Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla).

Figura 3. *Platyla merillaensis* n. sp. Paratipo (Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla).

riverbed. The Covallarco area is a relatively large karstic system, with two openings situated close together. The system is excavated in massive limestones of Aptian age, with reef facies. It is an active hydrological network, composed by different levels, some of them fossil, with predominance of strong sloped galleries and internal wells. The lower levels are active and are frequently flooded, thus disconnecting the communication among different parts of the cavity.

The Upper Covallarco opening is low and wide, opens into a descending corridor, which is covered in the initial stretch by a cone of alluvial debris. It ends in a flatter sector, which opens to the left to a gallery covered by gours and pavimental accretions. In the inner part it connects, through a chasm, with the galleries of the lower level. The point of collection of the shells registered 95-97% humidity, and a temperature of 13.5-14°C.

Etymology: The name refers to the locality nearest to the entrance of the cave.

Description: Shell small, subcylindrical, smooth and shiny, whitish in color. Protoconch short, with a very small nucleus, a diameter of about 500 μm and somewhat more than one spire whorl, with an irregular pitted microsculpture, very marked on the initial part (Figures 2D-E) and fading later (Figures 2F-G). Teleoconch with about four slightly convex whorls, a well-defined suture, lacking microsculpture except for some slightly prosocline growth lines. Aperture ovoid, sharp in the upper part; periostome simple. Columella orthocline, projecting outwards, covering the umbilicus which is reduced to a narrow groove.

Dimensions: The holotype is 2.24 mm high and has a diameter of 1.11 mm.

Measurements: Table I shows the dimensions of fully grown adults. The

most evident metric traits are a reduced elongation, since it is only two times longer than wide ($L/D_{\text{mx}}=2$), and the length always below 2.5mm.

Habitat: This species is found in the interior sector of the Covallarco cave. Specimens were found in accumulations of sediments in narrow and deep crevices. No shells were found in the entrance of the cave.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Discussion: Some congeneric species of *Platyla merillaensis* n. sp. are known in the Iberian peninsula, but the latter differs from all others by a shorter spire, absence of cervical callosity, and by having a translucent or whitish colour.

Measurements of this species are also very distinctive, with a length

Table I. Morphometry of the shell of *Platyla merillaensis* n. sp. Min: minimum, Mx: maximum, AV: average, SD: standard deviation, COEF, VAR: variance coefficient, L: length, D: diameter, Ha: aperture height, Wa: aperture width.

Tabla I. Morfometría de la concha de *Platyla merillaensis* n. sp. Min: mínimo, Mx: máximo, AV: media, SD: desviación estándar, COEF. VAR: coeficiente de variación, L: longitud, D: diámetro, Ha: altura boca, Wa: anchura boca.

N=10	Min	Mx	AV	SD	COEF. VAR.
D	1.02	1.19	1.117	0.0618	0.055
L	1.96	2.45	2.234	0.1427	0.063
Ha	0.58	0.79	0.640	0.0704	0.110
Wa	0.70	0.85	0.769	0.0484	0.063

Figure 4. Interior of Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla.

Figura 4. Interior de la Cueva de Covallarco, Merilla.

always under 2.5 mm, while the elongation (2.0) safely distinguishes it from other species of North of Spain: *Platyla callostoma* (length: 4.2 mm; diameter: 1.1

mm; elongation: 3.8); *Platyla cryptomena* (3.0 and 1.1 mm, elongation: 2.7); and *Platyla dupuyi* (3.6 and 1.0 mm, elongation: 3.6) (CADEVALL Y OROZCO, 2016).

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ALTABA C.R. 2013. A new species of *Platyla* (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Aciculidae) fills a biogeographic gap in the Mediterranean. *Zootaxa*, 3683 (1): 87-91.
- ALTONAGA K., GÓMEZ B., MARTÍN R., PRIETO C., PUENTE A. & RALLO A. 1994. *Estudio faunístico y biogeográfico de los moluscos terrestres del norte de la península Ibérica*. Parlamento Vasco, Vitoria-Gasteiz. 503 pp.
- BECH M. 1990. Fauna malacològica de Catalunya. Mol·luscs terrestres i d'aigua dolça. *Treballs de l'Institut Català d'Història Natural*, 12: 1-229
- BOETERS H.D., GITTENBERGER E. & SUBAI P. 1989. Die Aciculidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda Prosobranchia). *Zoologische Verhandelingen*, 252: 1-234.
- CADEVALL J. & OROZCO A. 2016. *Caracoles y babosas de la península Ibérica y Baleares*. Eds. Omega, Barcelona. 817 pp.
- GITTENBERGER E. 1991. Two more *Menkia* species (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Aciculidae) *Zoologische Mededelingen*, 65: 251-255.
- MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ A. & ROBLES F. 2005. Los Caenogastropoda terrestres (Mollusca, Orthogastropoda) de la Comunidad Valenciana (España). *Iberus*, 23: 7-24.
- ROLÁN E. 2003. Nueva información sobre el género *Menkia* (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia: Aciculidae) en Asturias. *Noticiario SEM*, 39: 64-66.
- TORRES ALBA J.S. 2012. Descripción de *Platyla hedionda* sp. nov. y nueva cita de *Acicula norrisi* Gittenberger et Boeters, 1977 (Gastropoda: Aciculidae) en la península Ibérica. *Spira* 4 (3-4): 101-104.
- WELTER-SCHULTES F.W. 2012. *European non-marine molluscs, a guide for species identification*. Planet Poster Editions, Göttingen, 679 pp.